

PART 2

GUIDELINES

2.1 Introduction

The following Guidelines were built based on the summary of findings of the MMM project, reported in Part 1 of this document, as a result of a previous literature analysis and empirical data collection through survey questionnaires and focus groups conducted in three target groups, namely Erasmus+ mobile students, staff, and specialists (psychologists and counsellors). Part 2 aims to provide guidelines for Erasmus+ mobile students, staff at international offices, mental health specialists (psychologists and counsellors), and Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) on the mental health of mobile students.

These guidelines serve as a comprehensive, evidence-based resource designed with three interconnected purposes:

1. Foundation for educational materials.

These guidelines form the cornerstone for all educational materials, the online platform, workshops, etc., to be developed, ensuring consistency and quality across all project outputs.

2. Europe-wide dissemination resource.

This document is designed for distribution across European HEIs to key stakeholders, including:

- Mobile students (incoming and outgoing).
- Psychologists and counsellors.
- International Relations offices and mobility coordinators.
- HEIs administrators and policymakers.

3. Strategic planning of mental health support.

These guidelines provide HEIs with practical frameworks for developing institutional strategies to prevent mental

health issues among Erasmus+ mobile students, moving beyond reactive approaches to proactive, systemic support.

The MMM project guidelines serve to understand, identify, and prevent challenges of the Erasmus+ mobile students' mental health. Specifically, they have four specific objectives. First, these guidelines aim to provide insights into the specific mental health difficulties faced by mobile students, including triggers/risk factors, protective factors, and coping mechanisms. Second, they help to identify existing gaps in support services. Third, they offer strategic directions for prevention, early intervention, and support. Finally, they emphasise proactive approaches that create supportive environments before crises emerge.

Ultimately, the guidelines proposed prioritise a practical, action-oriented approach. They suggest frameworks that can be adapted to the institutional context to develop a strategy and make it accessible to professionals across multiple roles in HEIs. Additionally, by providing evidence-based insights, the MMM guidelines contribute to a broader vision: a European higher education area in which **students' mobility is not only academically enriching but also psychologically supportive**. Through collective effort, HEIs can ensure that mobile students thrive academically, socially, and emotionally during their international experiences.

The following sections provide detailed guidance on understanding, identifying, and preventing mental health issues among Erasmus+ mobile students, with specific directions tailored to different stakeholder groups within HEIs.

2.2 Guidelines for Students, Specialists, and Higher Education Institutions Regarding Mobile Students' Mental Health

Overall, the MMM project identifies mobility as a sequence of psychologically sensitive transitions that require preventive and management actions tailored to each stage. Targeted interventions before, during, and after the mobility are essential to improve students' well-being and overall mobility experiences. This section summarises the key findings that underpin these conclusions and outlines their practical implications for students, support staff, and institutions.

Key Findings:

- **Mobile students experience multiple and intense difficulties** across all stages of mobility, especially in the domains of mental health, academic demands, and somatic well-being. Stress, anxiety, tiredness, rumination, cognitive fatigue, and loneliness were consistently identified by students, psychologists, and Erasmus+ staff as the most frequent and intense difficulties.
- **Additional common difficulties** include social integration problems, academic challenges, language barriers, and unhealthy behaviours.
- **These difficulties are closely linked to a range of triggers**, such as:
 - Social integration problems, exclusion, cultural and language barriers, homesickness.
 - Poor or scarce housing.
 - Bureaucratic delays or unclear procedures.
 - Financial strain.
 - Academic overload, assessment mismatches, and fear of presenting in a non-native language.
 - Personal vulnerabilities (e.g., anxiety, perfectionism, low self-esteem), traumatic events, and seasonality.
- **Stress related to social, academic, or financial pressure** was identified across all mobility stages (before, during, after) as the most harmful difficulty.
- **Gender differences** were observed: women experienced more difficulties across all stages and higher cognitive stress.
- **Non-European and culturally distant students** reported greater social and cultural challenges, including discrimination,

acculturation stress, intensified loneliness, and economic difficulties.

- **Socio-cultural difficulties vary by mobility stage**, tending to be more intense before departure and after return, and somewhat less intense during the stay abroad.
- **Students and specialists reported a wide range of coping mechanisms**, including social support (family, friends, housemates, ESN), physical activity, mindfulness, journalling, creative hobbies, planning tools, routines, and—when needed—professional psychological support. Specialists highlighted the value of routines, exercise, peer networks, and buddy/alumni schemes, while noting that early detection of difficulties remains a challenge.

Implications and Recommended Actions:

- **Prioritise early identification**, using psychological self-assessment tools that can help students detect emotional, academic, or social difficulties before they escalate.
- **Give special attention to stress management**, as stress related to social, academic, or financial pressure is the most harmful difficulty across all mobility stages.
- **Promote self-awareness and early help-seeking**, especially for women, who experience higher levels of difficulty. Students should be encouraged to:
 - Monitor their emotional well-being.
 - Respond to early signs of stress or anxiety.
 - Contact university psychologists or support services promptly.
 - Consult international coordinators when stress arises from administrative issues.
- **Support non-European and culturally distant students** by:
 - Normalising culture-shock and acculturation symptoms.
 - Connecting them with others who share similar experiences.
 - Encouraging cultural preparation (local norms, communication styles, academic expectations).
- Clarifying financial expectations (scholarships, cost of living, extra expenses).
- Promoting early use of university support, especially when experiencing severe anxiety or depressive thoughts.
- **Establish support networks at each mobility stage** (before the mobility, during the mobility, and after the mobility) to match the changing nature of socio-cultural and emotional difficulties. Coping strategies and guidance should be adapted to the specific needs of each stage.
- **Integrate effective coping strategies into support programmes**, such as social support systems, routines, exercise, peer networks, mindfulness tools, and buddy/alumni schemes.

2.2.1 Guidelines for Mobile Students (Incoming and Outgoing)

2.2.1.1 Main Difficulties

Before the mobility

- Recognise that emotional difficulties (stress, anxiety, tiredness, rumination, cognitive fatigue and loneliness) are normal responses to upcoming mobility.
- Recognise and understand that mental health difficulties before the mobility are common and may be higher than the actual difficulties during the mobility period. You should also expect difficulties upon returning (reverse culture shock).
- Prepare students psychologically for mobility: learn and practice stress and anxiety management techniques (e.g., breathing exercises, mindfulness, progressive muscle relaxation, etc.) and develop a personal stress management coping strategies toolkit. Also, prepare by creating realistic plans for budgeting, academic load, and social expectations.
- Contact former mobile students to normalise feelings about the upcoming change. Seek psychological help early if difficulties become overwhelming.
- Contact the International Office to clarify academic requirements, financial support, opportunities, etc.

During the mobility

- Be aware that low self-esteem is common during the mobility due to unfamiliar environments and cultural changes, among other aspects.
- Tiredness and cognitive fatigue are reported by many mobile students, therefore prioritise sleep and breaks. Establish daily routines that include

anxiety and stress reduction activities.

- Meet up with friends/family regularly to overcome homesickness and/or join student groups or activities to reduce loneliness.
- Contact academic advisors for help when studying requirements become unclear or difficult to manage.
- Recognise early signs of anxiety or stress and seek professional psychological help early if difficulties become overwhelming. Do not hesitate to contact counselling services, especially, if anxiety, rumination, or cognitive fatigue become persistent.

After the mobility

- Returning home can cause renewed academic and social pressure; therefore, it takes time to adjust.
- Loneliness after returning is common, you need to re-establish routines and keep in contact with friends from the mobility to ease the transition, especially for bachelor students, as the results revealed that this group experiences socio-cultural difficulties more intensely after mobility.
- Seek opportunities to integrate experiences (e.g., presentations, mentoring other students in/pre-mobility, etc.).

2.2.1.2 Main Triggers and Risk Factors

- Keep in mind that there are several triggers or risk factors that can affect your mental health. To reduce them make sure you participate in several activities, strengthen personal resources through personal development, and seek help and information.
- Make sure you balance your study periods with your leisure time. For that you should set clear boundaries between study and rest and take breaks while studying to reduce fatigue and stress.

2.2.1.3 Protective Factors and Coping Strategies

- Strengthen social support by actively maintaining contact with family and friends, especially at the beginning of the mobility period. Also, engage in joint activities and participate in buddy programmes and other integration activities to reduce loneliness and find new friends.
- Incorporate physical activity and sports into daily routine, as regular activities (walking, yoga, running, or other sports) to help reduce anxiety and improve sleep. Regular breathing exercises and mindfulness practices also support emotional stability.
- Use planning and self-reflection methods, such as to-do lists, weekly plans, and structured daily schedule tools, to maintain a sense of control. Journalling and creative activities are also effective.
- Seek help earlier, not only in a crisis: contact therapists, psychologists, doctors when emotional symptoms begin to interfere with daily life, do not wait until they become difficult to manage. Before the mobility, you should familiarise yourself with the university's psychological support system, especially if you receive such support before the mobility, too.
- Use cognitive reframing strategies. Practice gratitude and acceptance and focus on what you can control. Reduce perfectionism, low self-esteem and fear of missing out.
- Prepare for mobility realistically, i.e., get familiarised with the country's culture, administrative requirements, accommodation conditions, academic requirements of the host institution, and participate in pre-arrival or pre-mobility events organised by the university (host and/or sending).

2.2.2 Guidelines for Psychologists and Counsellors

2.2.2.1 Main Difficulties

Preparation

- Support services should apply a three-stage mental health support model: interventions to address issues related to difficulties before the mobility, during the mobility, and after the mobility, recognising that more attention needs to be paid before and after the mobility (allocate more resources).
- Specialists should develop and use mobility-specific mental health protocols, integrating different types of mobility-related difficulties (mental health, somatic, behavioural, academic, relationship, social, and cultural) into their assessment frameworks and/or service protocols.
- Service providers should prepare plans for interventions, acknowledging that emotional difficulties, such as stress, anxiety, and loneliness, occur at high rates. Services should, therefore, reflect and respond to these prevalence levels.
- Students from very distant countries (physically and culturally) should be considered as a higher risk group. The possible level of discrimination and isolation must be assessed.

Expansion of services

- As psychologists and staff emphasised, services should ensure culturally sensitive psychological support and accessible multilingual counselling that match the needs of mobile students. It is also essential to avoid misinterpretations (e.g., students' behaviour in a horizontal collectivist culture should not be interpreted as closedness).
- Focus on the topic of "reverse cultural shock" by counselling students on the psychological dynamics of returning home (e.g., disorientation, misfit of expectations, and identity changes) and

helping them normalise their experiences and reduce anxiety.

- It is crucial to ensure collaborative monitoring systems. Cooperation between psychologists and International Relations Offices allows them to receive timely information on at-risk students or those reporting significant emotional challenges abroad. In fact, psychologists and staff reported that they face persistent challenges such as students' reluctance to disclose difficulties and late help-seeking.
- Prioritise anxiety and stress management as core competencies in providing services for mobile students.
- Screen all mobile students for anxiety, stress, and rumination at intake, because early emotional profiling was reported as one of the keys to promoting resilience and belonging.

Preventive interventions

- Offer pre-mobility workshops on emotional preparation, anxiety, and stress management (e.g., breathing techniques, cognitive restructuring, etc.) and provide psychoeducation on the difference between ordinary adjustment to stress and clinical symptoms.
- Develop specialised group interventions for common difficulties (anxiety management, homesickness, or loneliness support groups, among others) or emotional support groups for students from culturally similar or contrasting regions. A sense of community reduces loneliness. Also, reintegration groups, especially for bachelor students, allow them to share their experiences and not feel alone. As reported, bachelor's students experience more intense socio-cultural difficulties after the mobility (e.g., return shock, reintegration problems, cultural disorientation, and disruption of social relations).
- In cooperation with other specialists, develop online resources accessible at all times (e.g., videos, topics, podcasts, guided meditations, self-help modules, etc.) by proposing content for these materials.

2.2.2.2 Main Triggers and Risk Factors

- The most frequent triggers named by mobile students are loneliness, intercultural barriers, social anxiety, and cognitive load, among other aspects should be considered. Students must be encouraged to participate in activities to reduce loneliness as well as develop time management strategies to help reduce cognitive load.
- Discuss with students stress and strategies related to long-distance relationships.

2.2.2.3 Protective Factors and Coping Strategies

- Integrate the used coping strategies of mobility students into the support, including topics such as social support, routine building, and physical activity, and also support reflection, mindfulness, and breathing techniques.
- Encourage self-regulation and structured planning by teaching time management, goal setting, and setting priorities. Offer individualised action plans to help maintain psychological well-being.
- Collaborate with international relations staff to ensure that students are provided with clear referral guidelines between institutions.
- Participate in training and improve professional qualifications on intercultural challenges to better identify risk factors of mobile students.
- Develop culturally sensitive interventions that consider cultural differences in help-seeking, stigma, or family roles, and use methods that support students' identity stability during times of change.

2.2.3 Guidelines for International Relations Offices and Mobility Coordinators

2.2.3.1 Main Difficulties

Before the mobility

- Integrate mental health preparation into pre-departure orientation sessions, particularly for students undertaking mobility for the first time, as survey results show that first-time participants report greater mental health difficulties than those with previous mobility experience. Integrate intercultural-preparedness training and tailor interventions to students' level of study, as bachelor's students typically have less intercultural experience and, therefore, require more psychoeducation in this area. Provide students with differentiated information for each mobility stage, acknowledging that challenges peak before and after the mobility.
- Create peer mentoring schemes/programmes and share testimonials from former mobility students about managing anxiety and stress. Provide realistic expectations about the emotional challenges of mobilities.
- Prepare specific guides for mobility students from non-European countries: social norms, communication etiquette, cultural differences, basic legal information, discrimination prevention, and postvention.
- Provide a draft with the current housing and living costs in order to help students plan the financial aspects of the mobility. Being informed means being prepared and reduces the stress.
- Offer insurance that covers mental health services if the existing insurance does not cover them (especially for students from non-EU countries).
- Initiate and distribute resources and programmes for stress and anxiety management to mobile students.

During the mobility

- Maintain contact with counselling services, academic advisors, and peer-support programmes to create a coordinated support system for students who experience difficulties.
- Ensure continuous communication and support services throughout the mobility cycle to avoid gaps in the transition from one stage to another. Contact students at high-risk periods (i.e., at the beginning of the mobility period, especially during the first weeks, and before their return). Maintain clear communication and respond quickly to reduce anxiety due to uncertainty.
- Ensure that orientation activities, cultural events, networking systems, and other events are systematically embedded into mobility programmes to reduce homesickness and loneliness. Organise social integration activities, especially at the beginning of the mobility period.
- Provide information about local mental health services in accessible formats (e.g., by collaborating with the host institution or offering remote psychological consultations from the sending organisation).
- Provide immediate support when students experience racism or other types of discrimination. Clearly communicate the incident reporting procedure and guarantees of anonymity.

After the mobility

- Before returning from the mobility, the home university should provide clear information about reintegration (especially for bachelor's students) and prepare short guides about what to expect upon return: emotional reactions, relationship changes, academic requirements, cultural reintegration shock, etc.
- Ensure that all returned students have access to reintegration resources such as reflective sessions, peer support networks, etc., given that emotional difficulties increase after returning.
- Organise post-mobility activities or offer re-entry programmes addressing reverse culture shock and readjustment stress.

- Incorporate structured feedback after the mobility and reflection processes to assess emotional well-being and identify stress or anxiety, because mobile students often experience repeated changes at HEIs or living environments. Assessment helps tailor support to ease these transitions.
- Create platforms for returned students to share experiences and stay connected or provide other opportunities to share mobility experiences with other students; this strengthens identity and gives meaning.
- Provide mentoring for returning students. More intensive mentoring is recommended for undergraduate students than for master's students.

2.2.3.2 Main Triggers and Risk Factors

- As staff attributed most problems to insufficient preparation, low autonomy, and opaque institutional communication rather than intrinsic student fragility, it is essential to encourage regular communication between students, teachers, staff and mobility coordinators.
- A buddy system with clear commitments (regular meetings and social tasks), mixed groups with local students rather than just Erasmus+ “bubbles”, and other similar measures could help reduce feelings of isolation as well as social integration & loneliness triggers.
- To reduce housing and accommodation triggers, sign agreements with reliable housing providers, guarantee accommodation for at least the first week of the mobility period, provide realistic price limits, and prevent fraud.
- Time management and procrastination/overwhelm triggers can be addressed by coordinating course schedules (so that everything does not happen at once) and clearly communicating deadlines and requirements to mobility students.
- Bureaucracy, administrative difficulties, and visa-

related triggers could be reduced by transparent processes, deadlines, and responsibilities (e.g., a single contact person for all the questions and clear step-by-step guides).

- Many risk factors frequently overlap (e.g., financial strain, loneliness, language barriers, and high stress), which means that a comprehensive, integrated approach is required. As a result, complex, multi-layered solutions are more effective than isolated, individual interventions.

2.2.3.3 Protective Factors and Coping Strategies

- Strengthen buddy, mentoring, and alumni schemes (e.g., ensure that every incoming student has a buddy contact). Involve alumni as information bridges, especially in the pre-arrival stage. Encourage group trips or activities with former Erasmus+ students.
- Create realistic pre-departure guides with clear academic, cultural, and practical information on accommodation, scholarships, documents, and studies. Make sure you organise pre-arrival sessions to reduce uncertainty, because clarity reduces anxiety and creates a sense of security.
- Strengthen regular and varied integrative activities (e.g., sports, cultural or academic activities).
- Collect systematic feedback from non-European students on discrimination and barriers to cultural adaptation.
- Improve cooperation between sending and host institutions by sharing student needs, creating standard support provisions and procedural maps.
- Learn to recognise subtle signs of risk by organising training on hidden risks, anxiety, social withdrawal, behavioural changes, etc.

2.2.4 Guidelines for Higher Education Institutions Administrators and Policymakers

Institutional policy:

- Develop and implement an integrated mental health promotion strategy that includes preventive measures, institutional interventions, and clear policies. Mental health aspects should be integrated, recognising that anxiety and stress are constant challenges across all mobility stages.
- Evaluate and improve social policies by integrating students' mental health provisions into HEIs' strategic documents. Policies should support accessibility and inclusivity to ensure that all mobile students have equal access to mental health support, accounting for linguistic, cultural, financial, and other barriers.
- Promote and ensure systemic support at the institutional level by strengthening international relations, student support services, and faculty and administration collaboration. Include mental health support as a criterion in partner institution selection.
- Increase the visibility of psychological services. Ensure easy access to psychologists and counsellors. Actively communicate about support options before, during, and after the mobility. Adopt unified procedures/protocols across departments for identifying and responding to mobility-related psychological difficulties.

Resource allocation:

- Allocate resources for comprehensive and psychologically supportive mobility to ensure funding and staffing for counselling services, peer support initiatives, mental health monitoring, and preventive interventions.
- Invest in staff training and support by providing ongoing professional development for teachers and administrative personnel on mobility-related mental health challenges. Training should include intercultural communication, intercultural psychology, recognition of risk signs, active listening, psychological crisis management, and specialised programmes such as Psychological First Aid. Psychological knowledge and intercultural competence training for staff would help reduce triggers and enable faster responses to the difficulties faced by mobile students.
- Creating culturally friendly HEIs spaces, as spaces where students can meet other students who have had similar experiences, would help reduce homesickness.
- Develop standardised procedures and clear referral systems: develop referral guidelines for mobile students and ensure fast response to psychological problems and crises. Develop a crisis management protocol for mobile students, especially those who are far from home.
- In general, increase the availability of psychological support at HEIs and improve the availability of psychological support in English.